

Towards developing a language model based expert system for computational simulations

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Abstract

We present an expert system framework based on small language models (SLMs) for computational simulations (which for this work is a Soderberg electrode model). The framework is developed with the vision that the user can use prompts in natural language to perform actions (setup and run simulations) and seek information (from sources about the model/technology). Once the user provides the prompt, the back-end of the framework automatically performs the analysis and provides the required output for the user. This is enabled by using a combination of approaches like agentic workflows, retrieval augmented generation (RAG), intent based knowledge graphs and custom tools. Evaluation of the proposed framework has shown that it can provide reliable responses with minimal hallucination when the user is seeking information. The ability of the framework to automatically and accurately execute a range of actions based on the prompt (including prompts with typos) is also demonstrated. The proposed framework is deployed locally to protect the user's data privacy. We envision that such a framework, due to its ease of use, could enable or increase the use of computational models (especially fast models) by process operators as decision support tools during operations in industry.

Keywords: Language models, Computational modelling, Agentic workflow, Retrieval augmented generation

1 Introduction

Computational simulations (or mathematical modelling) are an important tool used in a multitude of industries, especially in metallurgy, to investigate the conditions within the reactor/equipment (e.g., furnaces and ladles). This knowledge is critical to gain insights into how process parameters impact product quality as well as for process control. These models essentially use numerical methods to solve governing equations (often coupled partial differential equations) relevant to the physical phenomena dominating the process. These models have been used successfully in literature to investigate various metallurgical processes that are governed by fluid flow, electromagnetism, heat and mass transport, see reviews like [1, 2].

To setup and run such models, in general, requires creating geometry, meshing, setting up boundary conditions in addition to providing the relevant numerical settings to solve the governing equations. These steps involved in setting up the simulations are often time-consuming and requires expertise in computational modelling. In addition, the user would also need to convert operational data to a bespoke 'structured' input format for the model. Although a Graphical User Interface (GUI) can be used to reduce the overhead in setting up and running such models, the process experts using these model would require training and for large number of inputs the GUI can quickly become complicated to navigate. As a result, computational models often remain out of reach for the process experts (like operators and metallurgists) who could exploit their predictive abilities for operational decision support (rather than relying solely on previous experiences).

With the advances in Language Models (LM) particularly in understanding natural language, they can be utilized to develop an interface to communicate with these models [3, 4]. These language models can be categorized into large (like GPT-4 from OpenAI [5]) and small language models (like Microsoft's Phi [6]), see [4, 7]. This classification is based on model specification i.e., a large language models (LLMs) have more than ten billion parameters and are trained on very large datasets when compared to small language models (SLMs) [4, 7]. The use of LLMs to setup and run models has been explored in several papers in the literature. Alexiadis et al. [8] developed a proof-of-concept using GPT-4 to generate geometries which were then meshed and used for solid mechanics simulations. Verduzco et al. [9] explored the possibility of using GPT-4 to generate input files used in molecular dynamics simulations. Kumar et al. [10] developed MYCRUNCHGPT, a framework using GPT-4 for Scientific Machine Learning, which was used for the design and optimization of 2D NACA airfoils as well as the creation and training of a physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) for lid-driven cavity flow problems. In the aforementioned frameworks, LLMs (specifically GPT-4) are scoped to provide relevant response based on instructions (also known as prompt engineering technique [4]). And in order to perform specific tasks like calculations or to run simulations, these frameworks call the APIs of the relevant third-party software, see [8, 10]. A limitation of these frameworks is that they do not have a knowledge base, so a user cannot get a factual response to a question from the framework if needed (as LMs tends to 'hallucinate' [4, 11]). For example, if the user would like to understand the features available in the framework proposed by [8], the user cannot get the relevant response from the framework as the LM (like

GPT-4 or Phi) does have access to the documentation to respond accurately. Interestingly LMs have been successfully used in specialized domains on knowledge-intensive applications to provide factual responses via Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) approaches [4, 12]. This approach reduces the propensity of LMs to 'hallucinate' and provides context-relevant answers based on knowledge provided without the need to retrain (commonly referred to as fine-tuning) the underlying language model [12]. It should be noted that LMs can also 'hallucinate' when used to perform specialized tasks. In such applications augmenting LMs with specific tools (called LLM agents) have been used, see [11]. Another drawback of frameworks based on LMs described in [8, 10] is related to privacy as the data is sent to OpenAI's servers when using GPT-4. This limitation can be mitigated with the significant advances made in abilities of the SLMs (like Microsoft's Phi [6]) along with the availability of tools to easily deploy these language models locally (like Ollama [13]), see [4, 7].

1.1 Aim and objective

Considering the developments in the domain of LMs, the use of computational models by the domain experts that are not simulation experts (e.g., like the process operators and metallurgists), in industry requires a framework that can :

- Use natural language to prompt/interact with the framework.
- Provide responses to questions based only on the provided knowledge source. These knowledge sources can be the user guides of the simulation framework as well as operation manuals and guidelines, databases and other knowledge sources.
- Be able to modify or update the input/operational data used by the model as well as run the simulation.
- Have guardrails to assess the validity of the user prompt and prevent unauthorized actions by the framework.
- Allow for visualization of key simulation outputs which are important for process operators.
- Use Small Language Models (SLMs), that can be deployed locally (with limited computational resources), to ensure privacy and mitigate man-in-the-middle security threats.

Such a framework can be broadly categorized as an expert system for modelling applications as it would allow users with ease to interactively run simulations [14]. This type of system would significantly reduce the training required to use the models and allow the process experts to effectively use these models as decision support tools while ensuring consistency of input data and privacy of output data. In this paper, we showcase a proof-of-concept (PoC) of a language model based expert system for a computational model.

2 Overview of the computational model

The computational model employed in this work is an electrode model which is used to simulate Söderberg electrodes. This electrode technology is commonly used in submerged-arc furnaces for the non-ferrous metals and ferroalloys production. Invented

in 1919, these electrodes have extensively been updated with research and development in electrode pastes, electrode design, operation and control, see [15, 16]. The electrodes used in industry now have diameters around 2 m and carry alternating current (AC) typically around 150 kA into the furnace [15]. The main risk encountered during operation of the electrode is its breakage, see [15, 17] for further information.

To mitigate the risk of electrode breakage, the conditions within the electrode during operation needs to be understood. In this context, electrode models are a crucial tool that can be used by the process operator/metallurgists as a decision support tool for efficient electrode management and develop operational procedures to reduce the risk of electrode breakages, see [18].

In this work, the Söderberg electrode model developed by SINTEF and Eramet Norway is used (initial version of the model is described in [19]). The electrode model predicts the transient evolution of temperature, paste, magnetic field, current and thermal stresses on an axisymmetric electrode during operation. The model uses operational data related to the electrode operations like electrode slip, holder motion, supplied current, casing and paste addition along with temperature dependent paste properties. Verification of the model against temperatures measured in industrial Söderberg electrodes during operation was performed in [20]. In the scope of this work, a benchmark case is selected (based on [20]) and three relevant inputs to the model can be changed (two operational inputs: electrode slip and supplied current; a boundary conditions: heat transfer around current clamps). The choice of the benchmark case represents the simulation scenario which represents the standard operating condition in the electrode. It should be highlighted that for this PoC just three model inputs can be modified, it can be easily extended to other operationally relevant inputs in future works.

3 The proposed framework

Based on the objectives described in Section.1.1, a framework is developed in Python with a user interface (UI) where the prompts can be provided in natural language. Once the prompt is given, it is initially analyzed to understand and classify it as information seeking or perform an action. This analysis of the prompt and its classification is performed using a SLM agents based workflow described in Section.3.1. If the prompt is information seeking, the Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) workflow (described in Section.3.2) is used. If the prompt is intended to perform/engage in an action, the workflow to change the inputs or run the simulation, described in Section.3.3, is used. The framework essentially allows the user to modify a few of the files or run the case when prompted to perform an action (see Section.3.3). Each time the framework is started or a new session is initialized, the framework sets up a new case based on the benchmark case. Once the simulation is run, the key simulations results are easily accessible via the user-interface using pyvista (for VTK files) [21] and matplotlib (for CSV files) [22]. It should be noted that the LMs were deployed locally using Ollama [13]. The schematic of the proposed framework is shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1 Overall schematic of the proposed framework. For further information of the various components of the framework please refer to Section 3.1 (Agentic workflow), Section 3.2 (Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) workflow) and Section 3.3 (intent recognition and executing actions). The modelling software in the schematic refers to the electrode model described in Section 2.

3.1 How to analyze the prompt using language models ?

The purpose of prompt analysis is twofold: (i) to classify the prompt as either information seeking (*Chat*) or action-oriented (*Execute*), and (ii) to extract the underlying task. The task extraction must also account for possible typos in the prompt, correcting them when necessary for Section 3.3.

To achieve this, we employ an *agentic* workflow, consisting of multiple interacting LM-powered agents. Each agent has a specified role along with a well-defined task and goal. Agents communicate sequentially, with the output of one passed as input to the next, until the overall objective of prompt analysis is achieved. In this PoC, three agent based *agentic* workflow (developed using CrewAI [23]) is used:

- Reasoning agent: This agent takes the prompt and uses *Chain-of-thought* (CoT) prompting technique to analyze and provide reasoning. The use of CoT prompting allows the LM to perform step-by-step reasoning based on the user specified instructions, see [24]. It should be noted that these instructions also includes directions to treat typos in the prompt. The use of CoT prompting allows the reasoning to be split into logical sequential steps. The SLM used for this agent is Microsoft’s Phi3:3.8b-mini (instruct version) [6].
- Classifier agent: This agent takes analysis from the reasoning agent and structures it into three fields: Classification, Reasoning and Task. The SLM used for this agent is IBM’s Granite3.3:2b [25].

- **Formatting agent:** This agent takes the information provided by the classifier agent and structures it into a valid structured output. The output is configured to be a JSON structure containing classification (*Chat* or *Execute*) and the extracted task. The SLM used for this agent is IBM’s Granite3.3:2b [25].

Splitting the analysis into three different agents has been observed during testing to provide a consistent and reliable results [7]. In this workflow, the analysis provided by the reasoning agent is essentially restructured by the remaining two agents. So the analysis of the reasoning agent is critical for the accuracy of the proposed *agentic* workflow. It should be noted that the sensitivity of the choice of the LM used for the reasoning agent is discussed later in this work (see Table.2).

3.2 Retrieval-augmented generation

For information seeking prompts, the Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) technique is used to generate accurate and knowledge grounded responses from the LM. The steps involved in the RAG are:

- **Document ingestion and database generation:** In this step, the documents which form the basis of the knowledge source for the framework is compiled. The knowledge sources relevant in this context are documentation of the framework, the electrode model user-guide in addition to Söderberg technology documentation. These documents, which are in PDF format, are converted to text using the Docling framework [26]. It should be noted that Docling allows the conversion of the text in the document but it does not convert/interpret images and plots in documents to text. The text generated is then *split* or *chunked* semantically using the semchunk library [27]. The chunks are then converted to numerical representations (vectors) using an *embedding model*. The *embedding model* in essence captures the semantic relationships between words, see [28]. The vector representation of all the chunks obtained using chunking is then stored in a *vector database* (Faiss library [29]).
- **Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG):** The RAG typically involves two stages: *retrieval* (identifying relevant chunks from the *vector database* for a given user prompt), and *generation* (using the retrieved chunks and the prompt to generate a response) [12, 30]. These stages are automated through a RAG chain, which can be invoked with the prompt to generate context grounded responses [30]. Variants of RAG have been widely discussed in literature [12]. In this work, an evaluation based variant of RAG is employed that consists of three steps:
 - Step 1 (Initial response generation): The user prompt is passed to the RAG chain, which generates an initial response.
 - Step 2 (Evaluation of the initial response): The response is assessed by a language model evaluator (often referred to as *LLM as a judge*, see [31]). The evaluator scores the initial response against the original prompt and retrieved context on two criteria relevant to this study: hallucination and clarity. In addition, the evaluator also provides suggestions for improvement. The scoring by the evaluator is guided by sequential and logical user instructions (via *Chain-of-thought* (CoT) prompting technique [24]).

- Step 3 (Final response generation): The RAG chain is re-invoked with a redefined prompt that includes the original prompt as well as the evaluator’s suggestions, producing the final response.

The RAG workflow in this study is implemented in LangChain [30, 32] and uses Meta’s Llama3.1:8b (instruct version) [33].

3.3 Intent recognition and user actions in the framework

In this PoC, the user can perform just four actions in the framework:

- Current data: A time series in Excel format specifying the current supplied to the electrode during operation.
- Electrode slip: A time series in Excel format describing the electrode slip during operation.
- Heat transfer at current clamps: The thermal boundary condition around the current clamps is defined using two parameters: heat transfer coefficient between electrode and current clamps, and cooling water temperature.
- Running the simulation: Execution of the model based on the available case setup. During execution, the simulation runs in the background, after which the framework is restarted to allow configuration and initiation of a new case or query to the knowledge sources.

For the prompts classified as *Execute*, the task extracted by the *agentic* workflow needs to be analyzed to match the task to the corresponding action. This can be done by recognizing the intent underlying the task. An intent based knowledge graph (see Fig.2) can be used in this context as it would relate the various task definitions to the corresponding actions in the framework (analogous to [34]). Each action (i.e., corresponding action label) is setup as a node in the intent based knowledge graph. Within each node, a user generated list of the task definitions (referred to as example tasks) is provided. The four nodes are connected to a parent node in the intent knowledge graph. It should be noted that the intent knowledge graph implemented in this work (see Fig.2) can be easily expanded to include other actions.

Based on the task retrieved by the *agentic* workflow (Section.3.1), the knowledge graph is searched to retrieve the closest example task and the corresponding node (or action label). This is essentially a similarity search for the closest example task in a vector database generated with the example sentences in the intent based knowledge graph, in Fig.2, built using Faiss library [29]. It should be mentioned that if the similarity/distance between the retrieved task and the closest example sentence is large, the parent node is selected (which does not have any associated action in the framework). This is a guardrail to ensure that if the task retrieved by the *agentic* workflow is not representative, none of the four workflows are executed.

Once the node or action label is chosen, the corresponding workflows are enabled using tools developed in LangChain [32]. For the workflow to ‘modify heat transfer around the current clamp’, a custom tool is employed to read, update, save an Excel file based on the two user-defined parameters. For the workflows ‘change electrode slip’ and ‘change current data’, a separate tool is used to store the operational Excel

Fig. 2 Intent based knowledge graph used in this work to map the various task definitions to the action labels in the framework. The parent node of the graph is shown in blue, the labels corresponding to the four actions are shown in green. A few samples of task definitions (or example tasks), which are user specified, are shown in yellow for each action label.

Fig. 3 Screenshot of the proposed framework showing the front-end where users can provide queries/prompts. It should be mentioned that users can visualize the simulation results (selected in 'Simulation data') in the 'Visualization' tab in the user interface.

time series data. The framework incorporates guardrails to ensure the consistency in the provided inputs (e.g., verification of the headers in uploaded files). The toolset is designed to be extensible and can be expanded as required by future developments of the framework (c.f., [11]). Finally, when the workflow to 'run simulation' is selected, the electrode model is executed by calling the solver executable.

4 Results and discussions

In this section, the results from the proposed framework are showcased. The user interface of the framework is shown in Fig.3. The user simply provides the input prompt and the framework handles the remaining steps described in the previous section automatically. This means that for queries seeking information, the framework

will provide the context grounded response without the need for any additional user input. While for action oriented prompts, the framework provides the relevant forms where the user can upload the data file or provide values to update the data used in the model. The framework can also be prompted to run the simulation which will result in automatically running the electrode model. For the demonstration, the proposed framework is deployed on a typical mid-range workstation (HP workstation with a NVIDIA Quadro P1000 GPU, with a 4 GB memory, and Intel Xeon W-2145 CPU, with a 62 GB memory).

Listing 1 Responses from the framework to prompts asking information about the framework and technology.

Prompt: what is this technology

Response : Søderberg electrodes are the dominant electrode systems technology in submerged arc furnaces for production of ferroalloys and non-ferrous metals.

Prompt: What input parameters can i change in the simulations ?

Response : Based on the provided information, it appears that only operational input data can be provided by the user for each simulation. These parameters include heat transfer around current clamps, current supply, and electrode slip.

The other input parameters in the model, such as paste properties and casing erosion, are fixed in the model and cannot be changed via the user interface at this time.

Prompt: How should the inputs be defined for current clamps heat transfer?

Response : To define the heat transfer around current clamps, you need to provide two input values:

1. The temperature of the cooling water in Celsius.
2. The heat transfer coefficient between the clamps and casing in W/m^2K .

These inputs should be provided as a single data point or a constant value for the entire operational window, as they are not time-dependent parameters.

Prompt: How should i give the current input data

Response : To provide the current input data for the simulation, you should give it as a time series data in an Excel file. The first column should be the time in seconds that starts from zero until the end of the operational window, and the second column should be the current data supplied to the electrode in A at the given time instance.

Results or responses generated by the proposed framework for prompts that are information seeking are shown in Listing 1-2. The prompts considered for this test are essentially queries that seeks information about Søderberg electrode technology, list of model inputs which can be changed and the format of these inputs. For these prompts, the framework is seen to provide context grounded responses (based on the documents provided to the framework), see Listing 1. The ability of the framework to not hallucinate when asked about information out of the scope the knowledge sources is also seen to be reasonable as shown in Listing2.

Listing 2 Responses from the framework for prompts asking information about topics outside the scope of the knowledge sources provided.

Prompt: what is a LLM ?

Response : I'm not aware of any information about LLM in relation to Sderberg electrodes . However, I can tell you that none of the references provided mention LLM. If you could provide more information or clarify what LLM refers to in this context, I'll do my best to help.

Prompt: Describe a car

Response : I'm an expert system for Sderberg electrode model, but I don't see any information related to cars in our database. Unfortunately, I won't be able to provide an answer to your question about what a car is. If you have a question related to the Sderberg electrode model or its applications, I'll do my best to help.

When prompted to perform an action, the framework identifies the user's intention and initiates the corresponding workflow (see Listing 3). For current data, the user uploads an Excel files with operational time series data; electrode slip follows an analogous interface and is therefore not shown separately. For heat transfer at the current clamps, the user specifies the cooling water temperature and heat transfer coefficient, which are used to update the model input file (called Inputs_simulation.xlsx). The user inputs are incorporated only if they pass the framework's guardrails, which ensure compatibility with the required input structure. When the framework is instructed to run the simulation, the model executes in the background while a new framework session is started, allowing the user to configure and launch additional simulations (see Listing 3). The ability of framework to correctly treat typos in the prompts, extract the correct task and execute the appropriate action is shown in Table.1.

Listing 3 Responses from the framework for prompts requesting an action in the framework along with the user interface to input new data to the simulation. The response from the framework contains the action label obtained from intent knowledge graph and the file (its path) modified/updated. Note that the response for prompts to run the simulation also provides a 'button' to start a new instance of the framework.

Prompt: let me change the heat transfer around current clamps in the model

Enter Overall heat transfer coefficient at current clamps (in $W/m^2 \cdot K$):

250

Enter temperature of cooling water (in $^{\circ}C$):

50

Successfully updated data

Response : Executed workflow: WF_heattransfer_currentclamps || File saved at Cases /2025-09-16_09:40:18/inputs/casedefault/Inputs_simulation.xlsx

Prompt: change current data

Select the operational data for current

Drag and drop file here
Limit 200MB per file • XLSX

Browse files

Input file - current.xlsx 39.2KB

×

Successfully updated data

Response : Executed workflow: WF_current || File saved at Cases/2025-09-16_09:40:18/inputs /casedefault/Data_current.xlsx

Prompt: change holder motion

Intent: ElectrodeWorkflowIntent

Response : Intent not recognized. Please rephrase your question.

Prompt: run simulation

Response : Executed workflow: WF_run_simulation || Running simulation at Cases/2025-09-16_09:40:18

The simulation is running now. Click to start new simulation/workflow

Prompts	Extracted task	Executed action label
let me change current data	Modify current data based on user's intent	WF_current
modify electrode slip	Adjust electrode slippage parameters	WF_electrodeslip
change heat transfer and clamps	Modify or implement heat transfer mechanisms involving clamps	WF_heattransfer_currentclamps
lets run the simulation	Perform simulation	WF_run_simulation

Table 1 The extracted task and action performed (based on the action label extracted from intent based knowledge graph, see Fig.2) by the proposed framework for various prompts with typos.

Despite the abilities of the proposed framework shown in Listing 1-3 and Table.1, the bottleneck in its abilities is related to the prompt classification into *Chat* or *Execute*. The risk of wrong classification should be minimized as it would cause unintended workflows to be executed. The ability to correctly classify the prompts is dependent on the choice of LM used in the reasoning agent as it provides the analysis that is restructured by the two remaining agents in the *agentic* workflow, see Section 3.1. The predictive ability of the *agentic* workflow based on the choice of the LM used in the reasoning agent is shown in Table.2. The results indicate that Gemma3:12b achieves more accurate prompt classification than smaller models such as Granite3.3:2b and Gemma3:4b. Notably, the use Phi3:3.8b-mini (instruct version) as the reasoning agent also seen to be able provide a reasonably accurate classification compared using other models. In terms of computational runtime, the agentic workflow requires approximately three to four times longer to generate outputs when the reasoning agent is Gemma3:12b compared to Granite3.3:2b. Considering both computational cost and predictive reliability, Phi3:3.8b-mini (instruct version) represents a suitable compromise for this application (based on the test cases evaluated). As small language models (SLMs) continue to improve, future developments of *agentic* workflows for similar applications should investigate the enhanced language understanding capabilities of newer models.

An important consideration in developing a language model based application is related to tendency of LMs to hallucinate [4, 11]. In the proposed framework, this risk is minimized by using the retrieval-augmented generation (RAG), as described in Section 3.2. RAG relies on the semantic chunking and on an embedding model to generate chunks and capture semantic relationships. The embedding model’s effectiveness directly influences the relevance and quality of the chunks retrieved during RAG [28]. Consequently, responses generated by the framework should be rigorously tested during development, and end users, such as process experts, should critically evaluate the outputs before deploying the framework in operational settings.

Finally, the reproducibility of the responses from the framework is important. In this work, we evaluated the reproducibility of the responses generated by: independent executions of the framework (similar to approach used in [11]) and re-phrasing the prompts. When executing the model, the final responses from the framework (for various prompts) were observed to be very similar in each attempt, see A. The framework also produces similar responses for differently worded or re-phrased prompts as seen in B.

5 Conclusions

In this work, we have demonstrated a proof-of-concept (PoC) language model based expert system for computational simulations. The framework allows the users to communicate and setup/run computational simulations using natural language prompts. This is made possible with a combination of approaches: agentic workflow, Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) technique, intent based knowledge graphs, action execution using tools. The framework employs small language models as it is developed to be run locally to protect the privacy of user data. Once the user provides

Prompts	<i>LM-1</i>	<i>LM-2</i>	<i>LM-3</i>	<i>LM-4</i>	<i>LM-5</i>	<i>LM-6</i>
A	Chat	Chat	N/A	Chat	Chat	Chat
B	Execute	Execute	Execute	Execute	Execute	Execute
C	Execute	Execute	Execute	Execute	Execute	Execute
D	Chat	Chat	Chat	Chat	Execute	Chat
E	Execute	Chat	Chat	Chat	Describe	Chat
F	Execute	Execute	Execute	Execute	Execute	Execute
G	Execute	Execute	Execute	Chat	Execute	Execute
H	Chat	Execute	Chat	Execute	Execute	Chat
I	Chat	Chat	Chat	Chat	Chat	Chat
J	Execute	Execute	Execute	Chat	Execute	Execute
K	Chat	Chat	Chat	Chat	Execute	Chat

The small language models (SLM) used in the analysis are: Granite3.3:2b(*LM-1*), Gemma3:4b(*LM-2*), Phi3:3.8b-mini instruct version (*LM-3*), Deepseek-r1:7b qwen-distill version(*LM-4*), Llama3.1:8b instruct version(*LM-5*), and Gemma3:12b(*LM-6*).

Prompt A: Explain current data

Prompt B: modify the electrode slip

Prompt C: change the current electrode slip

Prompt D: tell me how to change current

Prompt E: How to modify electrode slip?

Prompt F: i want to change the simulation data

Prompt G: let me change the electrode data in the simulation

Prompt H: How can I change the current input data

Prompt I: Explain how to modify current data

Prompt J: i would like to alter the current electrode slip data in the model

Prompt K: Explain the parameters that I can change in the model

Table 2 Comparison of the predicted classification (*Chat* or *Execute*) of prompts by the *agentic* workflow based on the choice of LM used for the reasoning agent. The LM used for the reasoning agent is varied between 2-12 billion parameter models. It should be noted that the incorrect classification is highlighted in red.

the prompt, the framework automatically analyzes it and then provides a grounded response or performs a relevant action (protected by guardrails) in the simulation.

The framework has been coupled to a computational model for Söderberg electrodes used in metallurgical industries (see [19, 20]). The framework allows process experts to inquire information (about the implemented features, input formats, technology) or perform actions (like change model inputs and run simulations). For the PoC, only four actions can be performed in the model: give new current/electrode slip data from operation, change boundary condition for heat transfer between current clamps-casing, and run the simulation. The number of actions that can be performed by the framework can easily be extended. The framework is seen to be able to respond reasonably to questions about the model inputs and Söderberg technology and not to hallucinate or respond to out-of-context topics. The ability of the framework to understand the underlying intent of the prompt (even if they contain typos) and run the corresponding action has also been evaluated.

The PoC demonstrates the promising abilities of the proposed framework as an expert system for computational simulations which can be prompted using natural language. The framework can also be extended to other computational simulations by setting up the appropriate knowledge sources and configuring relevant actions. Such

a framework has the potential to substantially reduce the learning curve for process experts (like metallurgists) in integrating computational models into operation for industrial decision support tools.

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Conflict of interest statement

On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

Appendix A Reproducibility of the responses during various executions of the framework

Listing A.1 Responses from the framework for a given prompts seeking information during three attempt/excecution of the framework.

Attempt 1: How should the inputs be defined for current clamps heat transfer?

Response : To define the heat transfer around current clamps, you need to provide two input values:

1. The temperature of the cooling water in Celsius.
2. The heat transfer coefficient between the clamps and casing in W/m^2K .

These inputs should be provided as a single data point or a constant value for the entire operational window, as they are not time-dependent parameters.

Attempt 2: How should the inputs be defined for current clamps heat transfer?

Response : To define the heat transfer around current clamps, you need to provide two input values:

1. The temperature of the cooling water in Celsius.
2. The heat transfer coefficient between the clamps and casing in W/m^2K .

These inputs should be used as defined parameters for the simulation.

Listing A.2 Responses from the framework for a given prompt (asking information about topics outside the scope of the knowledge sources) during three attempt/excecution of the framework.

Attempt 1: what is a LLM ?

Response : I'm not aware of any information about LLM in relation to Soderberg electrodes. However, I can tell you that none of the references provided mention LLM. If you could provide more information or clarify what LLM refers to in this context, I'll do my best to help.

Attempt 2: what is a LLM ?

Response : I'm an expert system for Soderberg electrode model. Unfortunately, I don't see any information about LLM in the provided references or related to the topic of Soderberg electrodes. However, based on general knowledge, LLM can stand for Large Language Model.

Appendix B Variation in the responses from the framework when using differently worded prompts

Listing B.1 Responses from the framework for various versions of the prompts asking information about the heat transfer boundary condition around current clamps.

Prompt: How should the inputs be defined for current clamps heat transfer?

Response : To define the heat transfer around current clamps, you need to provide two input values:

1. The temperature of the cooling water in Celsius.
2. The heat transfer coefficient between the clamps and casing in W/m^2K .

These inputs should be used as defined parameters for the simulation.

Prompt: List the current clamp heat transfer model inputs

Response : To accurately simulate heat transfer around current clamps in the Soderberg electrode model, you need to provide the following two input parameters:

1. Temperature of cooling water
2. Heat transfer coefficient between clamps and casing (defined in terms of W/m^2K)

Prompt: Give me the inputs for the heat transfer around current clamps

Response : To accurately simulate heat transfer around current clamps in the Soderberg electrode model, you need to provide the following two input parameters:

1. Temperature of cooling water: This should be provided in Celsius.
2. Heat transfer coefficient between clamps and casing: This is defined as W/m^2K (watts per square meter Kelvin).

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